

Supplementary Material

1. Additional information on scenario implementation

1.1. Land, labor and capital intensities

Land, labor and capital intensities are modeled as exogenous target values that are approached by 2100, starting from the initial values. The target values are calculated with the respective growth rates for changes in either productivity or intensity, considering that intensity = 1/productivity. Target land intensities for 2100 are multiplied by a factor <1 to reflect the environmental impact of dietary changes. All values are given in Table 1 of the main text.

1.2. Changes in the A matrix and the consumption vectors

During the simulation, the initial values of the A matrix approach target values defined for the year 2100 in the target A matrix while the initial consumption vectors of households, governments and investment approach target consumption vectors in 2100.

These target values are obtained through various conversions of the original A matrix and the initial consumption vectors.

First, the monetary inputs belonging to the energy sectors (row numbers 3, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20) of the A matrix, and the shares of the energy sectors in the consumption vectors, are converted into biophysical inputs using conversion factors that relate the monetary with the biophysical output of every energy sector.

Second, inputs from less efficient or scalable renewable energy technologies (sectors 16, 19, 20) are shifted to other renewable energy sectors (sectors 14, 15, 17).

Third, a certain percentage of the inputs (in the case of the consumption vectors, expenditure shares) from the fossil and nuclear electricity sector (number 12 and 13), which depends on the respective scenario, is shifted to renewable energies (sectors 14, 15, 17), and a certain percentage of the inputs of the non-electricity energy sectors (number 3 and 10) is shifted to renewable electricity (sectors 15 and 17) after the application of a correction factor that reflects assumed energy efficiency gains through electrification processes.

Last, in the case of the A matrix, all the inputs to the service sector (number 7) are multiplied by a material intensity factor to reflect improvements or deteriorations in the material intensity of the service economy, while in the case of the consumption vector of the richest households, half of the consumption expenditure share for the food sector is shifted to the service sector, given that the consumption vector remains constant above a

threshold per capita consumption of 24,673 € per year which without correction could lead to an overestimation of food expenditures in scenarios with high economic growth during the 21st century.

1.3. Endogenization of energy intensities

While energy intensities can be modeled exogenously through the target A matrix, for the SSP implementations we changed the model structure of MORDRED to reflect endogenous changes in the energy intensity of the economy.

The main assumption behind the endogenization of energy intensities is that as productive capacities (measured as sectoral output per capita) increase, technological know-how increases as well, which leads to an improvement in energy intensities. Evidently, the opposite is true for a decline in productive capacities.

Consequently, we model the development of energy intensities with an energy intensity multiplier (*EIM*) for all the sectors (*s*) relevant to the SSP storyline implementations, i.e. the industry sector (sector 5), the services sector (sector 7), the transport sector (sector 21) and the main energy sectors (3, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17). The multiplier can be expressed as:

$$EIM_s(\text{output per capita}_s) = \beta_{1_s} * \text{output per capita}_s^{\beta_2} + \beta_{3_s}$$

The parameters are calibrated such that the function equals 1 at the initial time step of the simulation. If the sectoral output per capita becomes greater (smaller) than the value corresponding to the initial moment *EIM* becomes <1 (>1).

In the adapted version of MORDRED, the dynamically changing *EIM* is multiplied with the rows of the A matrix corresponding to the energy sectors (3, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20) in the case of all sectors for which energy intensities are endogenized (3, 5, 7, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17).

2. Development of energy intensities in SSP variations

Suppl. Figure 1: Changes in energy intensities for different energy types and in different sectors across the SSP simulations (SSP2': dark blue; SSP2'': lighter blue; SSP3': grey; SSP3'': beige; SSP5': red; SSP5'': pink). a) fossil energy intensity, b) biomass energy intensity, c) fossil electricity intensity, d) wind electricity intensity of the industry sector; e) fossil energy intensity, f) biomass energy intensity, g) fossil electricity intensity, h) wind electricity intensity of the service sector; i) fossil energy intensity, j) biomass energy intensity, k) fossil electricity intensity, l) wind electricity intensity of the

transport sector; m) fossil energy intensity, n) biomass energy intensity, o) fossil electricity intensity, p) wind electricity intensity of the fossil energy sector.

3. Scenario variations

To test whether historical discontinuities also appear under a partial introduction of biophysical limits, additional SSP variations were simulated in which either climate impacts or rising fossil fuel extraction costs were considered independently. The inclusion of climate damage factors alone is sufficient to considerably slow the growth of global final demand and average consumption. However, no ‘tipping’ point is reached; hence, there is no radical discontinuity in demographic developments in SSP2 and SSP3. By contrast, the introduction of steeply rising fossil extraction costs generates a feedback effect strong enough to reach a global socio-economic ‘tipping point,’ although the demographic collapse in SSP2 and SSP3 occurs later than in the SSP variations with full integration of biophysical feedback. For SSP5, no significant difference in demographic development is observed between the scenarios with complete and partial inclusion of feedback mechanisms. The scenario outcomes for the key variables are displayed in Suppl. Figure 2.

Suppl. Figure 2: Evolution of global final demand (a-c), world average consumption (d-f) and world population (g-h) in all SSP variations. Lines depict the SSP' and SSP'' variations discussed in the main text (SSP2': dark blue, SSP2'': lighter blue, SSP3': grey, SSP3'': beige, SSP5': red, SSP5'': pink). Circles depict the results for SSP variations in which the climate damages represented in MORDRED are activated while rising fossil extraction costs are deactivated. Triangles depict the results for SSP variations in which there are no climate damages but increasing fossil fuel extraction costs.